

Understanding Teacher Well-Being: Interplay of Emotional Intelligence, Music, and Mental Imagery

Sahrish Riaz^a
Dr. Hina Rana^b
Saba Walayat^c

Abstract

The aim of the present study was to determine the relationship among emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery, and psychological distress in teachers. Cross-sectional correlation research design was used by employing purposive sampling. The data was collected from N= 276, women (n= 158) and men (n= 118) teachers of colleges and universities having age range of 25-55 years. Standardized measurement tools Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test, Short test of Music Preference, Spontaneous Use of Imagery Scale and Kessler Psychological Distress Scale were used in the current study to measure the target variables. Demographic and information sheet devised by the researcher was used to assess the variables. The data was computed through SPSS-21. Frequency, reliability, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Hierarchical Regression were applied. The results directed that there was a significant negative relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological distress. Whereas significant positive relationship between visual mental imagery and psychological distress. Emotional intelligence and visual mental imagery were significant predictors of psychological distress. Visual mental imagery and psychological distress are more in women teachers as comparatively men teacher. Teachers from private sector are more emotionally intelligent and have more music preferences than government sector. Visual mental imagery is more to be found in teachers from government sector. The findings are useful for clinical psychologists who are able to suggest effective coping strategies for teachers to deal daily life stressors.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery, psychological distress, teachers

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^{a,b,c} University of Management and Technology, Pakistan | email: saba.walayat@umt.edu.pk

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INTRODUCTION

A teacher is someone who helps students in acquiring information, skills, or morals. The most important element in a student's education is their teacher. Without the role of teachers who grow knowledge into material that may be assumed, no matter how effective any educational programme featured in the curriculum is, it will mean nothing to students (Alsubaie, 2016). They must have a strong personality, psychologically or physically. But with burden of work place and managing home chores teachers are the one who undergoes with so much pressure and stress which leads them to psychological distress. Likewise, Pakistan is an emerging country whereas not just this, teacher here have religious, cultural, social, and economic differences. So teachers here have to face a lot of difficulties at home and at workplace as a study have shown that women teacher in Pakistan are about to 59% while male teacher make up to 41% accordingly (Ashraf, 2021).

As a teacher profession they undergo a lot of pressure in work place and at home as well so for that it matters a lot how they cope up with the stress and pressure so that affect their working ability. As we know that understanding one's own emotions as well as those of those around one is a sign of emotional intelligence. The idea of emotional intelligence states that people need to have a self-awareness that allows them to recognize feelings and control their emotions (Serrat, 2017). The effectiveness of teachers and the idea of emotional intelligence are examined in college and university classrooms. Role and potential of teachers, results of programs to improve emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence, proactive coping, burnout, supervisor support, and suggestions for enhancing teachers' situation (Ramana, 2013).

Emotional intelligence is capacity to apprehend, to use, and control one's own emotions in order to reduce stress, communicate clearly, empathize with others, overcome difficulties, and diffuse conflict (Segal et al., 2021). Emotional Intelligence in teachers is the most important attribute and the notion is being supported by significant research evidence. Linda Darling-Hammond (1997) claims that, outside of the home environment, the teacher has the greatest influence on students' achievement. The specific characteristics of teachers who are more effective than others have been the subject of numerous studies. In the past ten years, studies have demonstrated that students perform better under the guidance of teachers who focus on building relationships while providing challenging and relevant instruction. Additional research shows that people with higher emotional intelligence make better managers, salespeople, and leaders, and that big businesses tend to hire them more frequently (Mérida-López et al., 2017).

Emotional intelligence has gained prominence in recent years as a predictor of adults' mental health, but little research has examined its role in adults' psychological development. The predictive power of perceived emotional intelligence relative to psychological adjustment was examined. The results suggest that perceptions of emotional intelligence are a reliable indicator of how well adults adjust (Salguero et al., 2012). Butler and Chinowsky (2006) claim that in order to identify and develop the capacity of future leaders, emotional intelligence traits are just as crucial as cognitive intelligence tests and participation. Work affect is an essential element of performance at work (Kafetsios & Zampetakis, 2008). Muchinsky (2000) says that, there are many different kinds of emotions, ranging from pleasurable experiences that are positive experiments in our existence to unpleasant ones that are the most harmful. Individuals' behaviour on the job is reflected by affective or emotional experiments conducted at work that result in cognition (Khalili, 2012).

Hochschild (1983) defines emotional intelligence as "the management of emotion to produce a publicly perceptible facial and bodily display of a personality." Emotion in the workplace is undoubtedly such a communicable phenomenon that it affects the emotions of other employees (Sauce, 2014). Goleman et al., (2001) stated that shared emotions are stronger in continuous groups. Emotional intelligence is a term used to describe the ability to solve problems and make wise decisions using logic and intuition (Brackett et al., 2011). The study of the psychological aspects influencing people's various musical tastes is known as music preference psychology. People around the world listen to music every day, and it has a variety of effects on them, including guiding emotions, fostering cognitive development, and allowing for self-expression (Rentfrow et al., 2011). Music preference help to increase intellectual development and ability (Miendlarzewska & Trost, 2014). There are several theories which enlighten the concept of music preference some of them are as below LeBlanc Interactive Theory which stated that Decisions about what kind of music to listen to depend on the interaction of the listener's characteristics and the input information, which includes the music inducement and the listener's surroundings. He described the concept of music preference as a demonstrated level of liking for specific musical stimuli (LeBlanc, 1984).

Music preference have a strong impact on adults which can be shown by the researches. Lonsdale (2018) steered a study that investigated the Relationship between alexithymia, trait emotional intelligence, and reasons why people listen to music. Results showed that those who scored highly on a test of alexithymia were more likely to use music for the same purposes, whereas those who were emotionally intelligent were less likely to do so. Kim and Kim, (2017) conducted a study to determine the effects of a music performance programme on aggression, anxiety, and emotional intelligence. However, there was no statistically significant change in the level of overall emotional intelligence, anxiety, or aggression after the musical instrument performance programme. However, it improves the ability to observe emotions and lessen physical and verbal antagonism. According to a study, learning music has the potential to profoundly alter people's social, emotional, cognitive, or physical states. Learning that transforms the learner in significant ways is called transformational learning. Finally, music studies may benefit motivation, socio-emotional growth, mental health and wellbeing, as well as pragmatic behavior throughout life (Hodges & Creech, 2021). According to studies, listening to music that one enjoys helps one stay happy or maintains one's mental health; conversely, listening to music one dislikes can make one feel down or depressed (Hargreaves & North, 1999).

Visual mental imagery denotes to how people think using visual, image-like internal mental representations. Mental imagery is the act of mentally creating images. These visuals may be imagined synthesized images or memories of previous visual experiences (Nanay, 2021). A weak form of perception, visual mental imagery is a depictive internal depiction. The primary visual cortex is where neural demonstrations of mental and perceptual images first resemble one another, according to brain imaging investigation (Pearson et al., 2015). Evidence from studies suggests that imagery stirs up more powerful feelings. It has been demonstrated that images have a stronger connection to emotional and physiological reactions than words (McEvoy et al., 2018). Taruffi and Küssner, (2015) steered a study that investigate It has been said that visual mental imagery, which entails "seeing" without a sensory stimulus, is a crucial aspect of our mental lives. However, little research has been done on the mechanisms underlying how visual mental images emerge while listening to music. The ability of music to conjure up images can be used both in regular life

and in therapeutic settings to maximize the advantages and reduce the drawbacks of visual mental imagery.

When you encounter stressors that you are unable to manage, it causes psychological distress. Traumatic events, significant life events, regular stressors like work stress, family stress, relationship stress, and health problems are all examples of stressors (WHO, 2012). The extent to which positive and negative affect at work mediate the effects of emotional intelligence on psychological distress. The results showed that only negative affect fully mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological distress. Additionally, the direct effect of emotional intelligence was stronger for positive affect than it was for negative affect (Karim, 2009). Higher emotional intelligence was thought to be linked with low levels of psychological distress and more adaptive but also less maladaptive coping (Campbell et al., 2007).

Numerous music and dance instructors reportedly use mental imagery in the preparation, execution, and assessment of their teaching and coaching. Athletes and dancers are frequently instructed by coaches and dance instructors to use imagery during practice, competition, and performance (Overby & Haslam, 1998). This current study is a way to check which factor contribute in psychological distress and how the variable under study impact on their psychological well-being does. Different factors can cause psychological distress in teachers some of them are explained by researches. The results of a pilot study on the relationship between teachers' psychological health and their classroom teaching and student development outcomes. Programs for mindfulness training may be a promising way to address the psychological stress and burnout that teachers frequently experience. This study shows that mindfulness training can help teachers prevent psychological distress and burnout by being effective and practical (Cheng et al., 2021). In a study, it was examined to what extent positive and negative affect at work mediate the effects of emotional intelligence on psychological distress. The findings demonstrated that only negative affect was fully capable of mediating the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological distress. Last but not least, negative affect had a significant direct impact on psychological distress (Karim, 2009).

The current study examined whether there is an association among emotional intelligence, musical preferences, visual mental imagery, and psychological distress in educators (H1). It was also investigated whether emotional intelligence and musical preferences predict visual mental imagery and psychological distress in educators (H2). Furthermore, the hypothesis that visual mental imagery mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence, musical preferences, and psychological distress in educators was tested (H3). Finally, it was explored whether gender and type of educational institution (public versus private) moderate these relationships, with expected differences across groups (H4).

METHODOLOGY

Cross-sectional correlation research design was employed to carry out current study. Purposive sampling technique was used to recruit the sample in the current study. Calculated through G-Power analysis by keeping medium effect size 0.3, probability of error .05 with power 95. Total sample size would be 111 and final sample size was also decided on the basis of existing literature. In the current study, total data comprised of $N= 276$. Participants were recruited from different private and public colleges and universities of Lahore city by including university and college

teachers where the institutions could be both public and private academic institutions with teachers age range of 25-55 years and also having at least regular teaching experience of more than 6 months were included. However, teachers taking any kind of psychological intervention from the past 6 months and with any physical disability was excluded. It was approved by the Ethics and Research Committee of the Faculty of Psychology at the Lahore School of Professional Studies, The University of Lahore.

Measures

Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT, Salovey and Mayer (1990)). The four subscales of the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test, created by Salovey and Mayer in 1990, are emotion perception, emotion use, self-emotion management, and emotion management of others. The SSEIT model and the EQ-I model of emotional intelligence are closely related. A scale from 1 for "strongly disagree" to 5 for "strongly agree" responses is used in the 33-item SSEIT self-report. The graded outcomes of each subtest are added to determine the participant's overall score. This tool has an internal consistency of .90. Items 5, 28, and 33 are reverse coded to determine the overall scale scores, which are then added together. Higher scores indicate more recognizable emotional intelligence. Scores can range from 33 to 165. Formal permission from the author was sought for translating and using the scale in the current study. The reliability of the scale in current study is $\alpha=.92$.

Short Test of Music Preferences (STOMP; Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003) The STOMP is a 14-item scale used to evaluate musical genre preferences. The scale used to evaluate preferences for 23 genres has been revised and is now known as the STOMPR. In the original draft, we identified four main dimensions of music preference. Scores can be between 14 and 98, and higher scores reflect more musical preferences. STOMP's psychometric development led to excellent first-order construct validity and reliability estimates. The STOMP had strong scale reliability with Cronbach's α equal to 0.85 (Rentfrow et al., 2011). Formal permission from the author was taken for translating and using the scale in the current study. The reliability of the scale in current study is $\alpha=.87$. Spontaneous Use of Imagery Scale (SUIS; Reisberg, Pearson, & Kosslyn, 2000) The 12-item SUIS questionnaire was created to assess how often people use spontaneous imagery in daily life. Participants rate the degree to which each item is appropriate for them using a 5-point scale (from never appropriate to always completely appropriate). The scale's cutoff point was 12, and the higher the score, the more mental imagery. The SUIS had convergent validity and acceptable reliability. The SUIS had strong scale reliability with Cronbach's α equal to 0.88 (Reisberg et al., 2003). Formal permission from the author was sought for translating and using the scale in the current study. The reliability of the scale in current study is $\alpha=.80$.

Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10; Kessler et al., 2003); a concise tool for measuring psychological distress is the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10). The K10 scale consists of 10 questions about various emotional states, each with a five-level response scale. To evaluate how much distress a person is experiencing, the test can be used as a quick screening tool. The questions can be read aloud to the patient or give them the form to fill out on their own. The K10 is a 10-item questionnaire that seeks to produce a general measure of distress by asking about anxiety and depressive symptoms experienced over the previous four weeks. The cut off score was 10-50 in which the higher the score the severe the distress. K10 had strong scale reliability with

Cronbach's α equal to 0.88 (Kessler et al., 2003). To translate and use the scale in the current study, the author's formal consent was requested. The reliability of the scale in current study is $\alpha=.91$.

RESULTS & FINDINGS

The descriptive analysis on emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery and psychological distress of the participants was carried out.

Table 1
Demographic Information (N=276)

Demographic Variables		n (%)
Teaching Sector	Government College	66(23.9)
	Private College	65(23.6)
	Government University	70(25.4)
	Private University	75(27.2)
Department	Faculty of Management Sciences	59(21.4)
	Faculty of Information Tech & Engineering	23(8.3)
	Faculty of Arts & Architecture and Law	42(15.20)
	Faculty of Language & Literature	42(15.20)
	Faculty of Pharmacy, Allied Health and Social Sciences	110(39.9)
Listening Music During Day	Not at all	32(11.6)
	Rarely	30(10.9)
	Sometimes	143(51.8)
	Often	71(25.7)
Interesting Situations to Listen to Music	In happiness & leisure	180(65.2)
	In sadness & trouble	55(19.9)
	More than one situation	41(14.9)
Feeling After Listening Music	Happiness & active	200(72.5)
	Sadness	33(12)
	Mixed emotions	43(15.6)

Note. Frequency and percentage of demographic variables have shown in the above table.

Table 1 shows that mostly teachers are doing job in private colleges and universities, belonged to faculty of social sciences, allied health and pharmacy. Majority of the sample reported that they listen music sometimes during a day and listen music in happy or leisure time.

Pearson Product Moment Co-Relation Analysis

In order to investigate the relationship among emotional intelligence, music preferences, visual mental imagery and psychological distress, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was conducted.

Table 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation among Emotional Intelligence, Music Preference, Visual Mental Imagery and Psychological Distress in Teachers (N=276)

Sr		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1.	Reflective Complex											1	.52**	.34**	.69**	-.12*	-.11
2.	Intense Rebellious												1	.44**	.52**	-.21**	-.02
3.	Upbeat Conventional													1	.40**	-.02	-.03
4.	Energetic Rhythmic														1	-.11	-.07
5.	Visual mental imagery															1	.29**
6.	Psychological distress																1

Note. *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001, Gender=Female=0, Male=1, Institute type=Private sector=0, Government sector=1, Family system=Nuclear=0, Joint=1, Duty hours=Morning=0, Evening=1, Listen music=Yes=0, No=1

Table 2 shows that gender has significant positive correlation with age, qualification, teaching experience, intense music, and rebellious music whereas significant negative correlation with spontaneous use of imagery and psychological distress. This means that in the current data men teachers are more in age, more educated, have more teaching experience, having intense as well as rebellious music preference whereas female have more imagery and psychological distress. Age has significant positive correlation with qualification, institute type, teaching experience, listening music, emotional intelligence and significant negative correlation with duty hours and psychological distress. By that it means with the more aged teachers are qualified and working in government sector, they have more teaching experience, they are more interested in listening music and with increasing in age they become more emotionally intelligent however as their age increase, they don't work in evening time while teachers form private sector are more interested in working in evening timings and their psychological distress is decreased by the increment of the age.

Qualification has significant positive correlation with institute type, teaching experience, emotional intelligence and whereas significant negative correlation with psychological distress. By that it means that government teachers are more qualified, have more working experience and highly qualified teachers are more emotionally intelligent however they have less psychological distress in them. Institute type has significant positive correlation with teaching experience, duty hours and significant negative correlation with emotional intelligence and music preference. This means that government teachers have more teaching experience and work in morning time while teachers of private sector are more emotionally intelligent and their music preferences are more. Teaching experience has significant positive relation with listening music and emotional intelligence and significant negative relation with duty hours, music preferences and psychological distress. It means that the teachers who have more experience are more prone to listen music and more emotionally intelligent while teachers who have shift in morning have more experience and their music preferences are less as well as their psychological distress.

Duty hours have significant positive relation with psychological distress and significant negative relation with emotionally intelligence. It means that the teachers who work in morning time have more psychological distress and teachers from morning time are more emotionally intelligence. Listening music have significant negative relation with music preferences. It means that the teachers who listen music on daily basis have more music preference. Emotionally intelligence have significant positive relation with music preference and significant negative relation with psychological distress. It means that if a teacher is emotionally intelligent their music preference is high whereas psychological distress decreased with higher emotional intelligence. Music preference have significant negative relation with imagery it means that the teachers who have

more music preference are less imagery. Spontaneous imagery scale has significant positive correlation with psychological distress. It means that with the increment of imagery in teachers may increases their psychological distress.

Hierarchical Regression Analysis

Hierarchical regression was done to assess the predictors of psychological distress.

Table 3

Hierarchical Regression to Assess Prediction of Psychological Distress (N= 276)

Variables	B	SE	β	95% CI	
				LL	UL
Model 1					
EI	-.16	.02	-.36***	-.21	-.11
R2	.13				
$\Delta R2$.12***				
F	39.8				
Model 2					
EI	-.16	.02	-.35	-.21	-.11
MP	-.01	.03	-.02	-.08	.06
R2	.13				
$\Delta R2$.12				
F	.10				
Model 3					
EI	-.16	.02	-.36***	-.21	-.11
MP	.01	.03	.02	-.05	.08
VIM	.28	.05	.30***	.18	.38
R2	.22				
$\Delta R2$.21***				
F	31.61				

Note. *** $p < .001$, CI= Confidence Interval; LL= Lower Limit; UL= Upper Limit, SE= Standard Error; EI= Emotional Intelligence; MP= Music Preference; VIM= Visual Mental Imagery

Above table 4.4 indicated that overall Model 1 explained 12% variance and emotional intelligence was a significant predictor of psychological distress with $F(1, 275) = 39.8, p < .001$. Model 2 explained 12% variance and music preference was not a significant predictor of psychological distress with $F(4, 271) = .10, p > .05$. Model 3 explained 21% variance and emotional intelligence as well as visual mental imagery were significant predictors of psychological distress with $F(1, 270) = 31.6, p < .001$.

Emergent Model of Regression

Figure 1. Showed that to access the prediction of psychological distress through emotional intelligence and visual mental imagery.

Meditation was conducted through Baron and Kenny but the assumption of it was not fulfilled.

Independent t-Test

Independent t-Test was done to assess the gender and institute type sector differences in emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery, and psychological distress.

Table 4

Independent Sample t-Test Showing Gender Difference of Emotional Intelligence, Music Preference, Visual Mental Imagery, and Psychological Distress in Teacher

Variables	Women n=158		Men n=118		t	p	95% C.I.	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
EI	121.24	19.57	121.94	21.38	-.28	.22	-5.58	4.17
MP	56.45	14.47	59.05	16.74	-1.38	.18	-6.31	1.10
VIM	43.62	8.41	40.18	11.24	2.90	.01*	1.11	5.7
PD	28.12	8.38	25.50	9.69	2.40	.02*	.47	4.7

Note. *p< .05; M=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation; CI= Confidence Interval; LL=Lower Limit; UL=Upper Limit; EI=Emotional Intelligence; MP=Music Preference; VIM=Visual Mental Imagery; PD=Psychological Distress

Results showed that the significant difference in visual mental imagery were found in women and men. It also signifies that women teacher have more visual mental imagery than men teachers $t(43.62) = 2.90, p<0.05[1.1, 5.7]$. Results also depicted that the significant differences in psychological distress were found among women and men. The result suggested that women teachers are more prone to experience psychological distress than men teachers $t(28.12) = 2.40, p<0.05[.47, 4.7]$. The result indicated that no significant differences are found in both genders on basis of emotional intelligence and music preference.

Table 5

Independent Sample t-Test Showing institute sector Difference of Emotional Intelligence, Music Preference, Visual Mental Imagery, and Psychological Distress in Teacher

Variables	Private n=140		Government n=136		t	p	95% C.I.	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
EI	125.70	18.86	117.26	20.96	3.51	.04*	3.71	13.16
MP	59.50	16.80	55.58	13.83	2.11	.03*	.26	7.57
VIM	41.52	11.34	42.80	8.03	-1.08	.02*	-3.62	1.04
PD	26.30	9.69	27.73	8.29	-1.32	.09	-3.57	.70

Note. *p< .05; M=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation; CI= Confidence Interval; LL=Lower Limit; UL=Upper Limit; EI=Emotional Intelligence; MP=Music Preference; VIM=Visual Mental Imagery; PD=Psychological Distress

Results showed that the significant difference in emotional intelligence were found among private and government (public) sector. It signifies that teacher from private sector are more emotionally intelligent than government sector $t(125.70) = 3.51, p<0.05[3.7, 13.16]$. Results showed that the significant difference in music preference were found among private and government (public) sector. It indicated that private teachers have more music preferences, they are interested in listening different type of genre of music $t(59.50) = 2.11, p<0.05[.26, 7.57]$. Results showed that the significant difference in visual mental imagery were found among private and government (public) sector. It indicated that government (public) teachers are more imaginary than private teachers $t(42.80) = -1.08, p<0.05[-3.62, 1.04]$. The result indicated that no significant difference is found in both private and government (public) sector on basis of psychological distress.

Discussion

The current study investigated the relationship among emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery, and psychological distress in teachers. In Pakistan many researches have been conducted on emotional intelligence and psychological distress of teachers. Some researches suggest the relationship between emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and psychological distress. Results indicated that higher the emotional intelligence more job satisfaction and less psychological stress where as some findings oppose that higher the emotional intelligence cause the psychological distress (Humaira et al., 2017; Karim, 2019). Limited researches being conducted on music preference, visual mental imagery and it's on affect psychological distress of teachers especially in Pakistan. The results of present study helped in better understanding how emotional intelligence of teachers being affected and for that what kind of music genre they prefer to listen and by listening music as well as what kind of visual images creates in mind and on that how does it effect on psychological distress of teachers. The importance of relationship among emotional intelligence, music preference, visual mental imagery and psychological distress was highlighted in the current study as far no definite link was being proposed before in Pakistan.

In current study the data was collected from public and private college and university teachers with age range of 25-55 years. Majority of them belongs to nuclear family system and listen music. In current research majority of teachers are female as compare to male. As many studies of Pakistan have also shown that female gender is more tend to have the teaching profession as they feel this profession secure (Noor, 2017; Sheikh et al., 2019; Kamran, 2015). The variables of the current study can be supported by a research in which was aimed to verify a model for handling psychological distress and investigate how using music as a coping mechanism affects the way stressors affect psychological distress (Kong & Wong, 2022). In this present research result psychological distress in teachers and emotional intelligence are significantly inversely correlated. Higher emotional intelligence would be associated with lower levels of psychological distress as well as more adaptive coping, but less maladaptive coping, which would support the current study's conclusion (Campbell & Ntobedzi, 2007). The present findings also supported by existing literature that only negative affect fully mediated the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological distress (Brackett et al., 2011). The inverse relationship between EI and psychological distress may be particularly relevant in Pakistan, where teachers often operate under resource constraints and socio-economic pressures. Developing EI could act as a buffer against these stressors.

Another finding of recent research indicated that there is a strong correlation between psychological distress and visual mental imagery. For teachers in Pakistan, EI may not only reduce distress directly but also facilitate the generation of more constructive mental images, enhancing coping and reducing the impact of stressful experiences. This finding is consistent with earlier findings that showed a link between the absence of positive mental images and the presence of negative mental images and the severity of psychological distress (Weßlau et al., 2015). Many researches can support the present finding that distressing mental images are common in psychological disorders and found to have an important role in the maintenance of anxiousness and other psychological problems (Hirsch & Holmes, 2007; Sirgy, 2012; Piveot, 2019). The current study also indicated that emotional intelligence and visual mental imagery were significant predictors of psychological distress. Outcome can be supported by the research which shows that EI and imagery are important thing in understanding the relationship between the stress and mental

health (Lintd, 2016). The link between negative imagery and psychological distress may be especially relevant in Pakistan, where teachers are exposed to stressful professional environments that can reinforce maladaptive mental images, thereby intensifying their distress.

Result of present study showed that visual mental imagery and psychological distress are more in women teacher as comparatively men teacher. Existing evidence showed that women abstract qualities are more which includes imagination. So, mental imagery can be foundation of stress in women (Devdio, 2019). In Pakistan, women teachers' heightened levels of mental imagery and psychological distress may reflect not only their greater imaginative tendencies but also the added social and familial pressures they encounter. The result of the present study also indicated that teacher from private sector are more emotionally intelligent and have more music preferences than government (public) sector. It can be justify by the research that was ample evidence to believe that MP and EI are related (Otchere, 2014). While another study confirmed the link between various musical contexts, music consumption, and individual variations in personality and trait emotional intelligence. Results revealed age had a negative impact on music consumption as well as significant positive effects of all music usage factors (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2012). Music preferences in Pakistan can be describe as Pakistani music is represented by a wide variety of forms. It ranges from traditional styles to Sufiyana Kalam which vary due to religious view to cultural preference (Ali, 2016).

CONCLUSION

This study is one of initial steps in determining the relationship of emotional intelligence, music preference and visual mental imagery and its psychological impact on college and university teachers. Teachers went through lot of pressure, stress and experience range of emotions so for their psychological well-being and increase in professional productivity, one need to work on emotional intelligence. Different workshops and seminars can be arranged and by using music which function as meditation for teachers in simple relaxation exercise for creating more positive imagery resultantly for the betterment of their psychological well-being. The present study is important for the success of any institute because psychological stress has a strong impact on life style and emotional intelligence of teachers. Emotional intelligence is very important for any teacher in an organization because their faculty (staff) make such decision which give benefit to the organization that how a teacher can control their psychological distress by using emotional intelligence, visual mental imagery and with their music preference as well.

Limitations and Future Directions

The present study was conducted on emotional intelligence, music preferences, visual mental imagery, and psychological distress of teachers. The results revealed that emotional intelligence have negative effect on the psychological distress whereas visual mental imagery have positive effect on psychological distress. Music preference also plays important role in emotional intelligence and psychological distress of teachers. The effect of demographics variables (i.e. gender, family system, qualification, institute and experience) was also assessed which showed that these have effect on psychological distress as well. Emotional intelligence and visual mental imagery play significant role in causing psychological distress in teachers.

There were some limitations in the current study which are as follow. Firstly, the sample was only collected from only one city i.e., Lahore and might not be true representative of the larger audience. It is suggested that for increasing the generalization of the results, data could be collected from different cities while making the data more representative. Secondly, there were some time restraints involved while collecting data. The data collection time was in summer break as data was meant to collect from colleges and universities. Many of the institutes were closed in summer break so that was hurdle in collecting data and data was comprised. It could be improved significantly while allowing the extended time period for data collection. Thirdly, as the population was the working class managing their immense workloads therefore performa's were given to many participants but because of their busy schedule, many teachers didn't return the filled form.

Competing Interests

The authors declared no known competing interests.

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